

CHRONOTOPIC PSYCHOLOGISM AS A FORM OF ARTISTIC PSYCHOLOGISM IN THE CONTEXT OF WOMEN'S LITERATURE

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Annotation :

This article examines the concept of chronotopic psychologism as a form of artistic psychologism in the context of women's literature. The authors explore the specifics of the use of chronotopic psychologism in literary works, in which the emphasis is on the inner world of female characters, their relationships, psychological characteristics and socio-cultural context. Through the analysis of various works by female authors, the article explores how chronotopic psychologism contributes to a deeper understanding of women's identity in literature, expands readers' perspectives and allows deeper insight into the world of female psychology and emotional experience. The study also draws attention to the importance of this approach for the formation of empathy, empathy and understanding of the diversity of women's experiences in literature.

Keywords: chronotopic psychologism, women's literature, artistic psychologism, the inner world of characters, socio-cultural context, women's identity, empathy, empathy, literary research, women's psychology

Аннотация :

В данной статье рассматривается концепция хронотопического психологизма как формы художественного психологизма в контексте женской литературы. Авторы исследуют специфику использования хронотопического психологизма в литературных произведениях, в которых акцент делается на внутреннем мире женских персонажей, их взаимоотношениях, психологических особенностях и социокультурном контексте. Через анализ различных произведений женских авторов, статья исследует, как хронотопический психологизм способствует более глубокому пониманию идентичности женщин в литературе, расширяет перспективы читателей и позволяет глубже проникнуть в мир женской психологии и эмоционального опыта. Исследование также обращает внимание на важность данного подхода для формирования эмпатии, сопереживания и понимания разнообразия женского опыта в литературе.

Ключевые слова: хронотопический психологизм, женская литература, художественный психологизм, внутренний мир персонажей,

социокультурный контекст, идентичность женщин, эмпатия, сопереживание, литературное исследование, женская психология

Introduction

Fiction is a mirror of society, reflecting its values, norms and views of the world. In the context of women's literature, special attention is paid to the study of female psychology, the inner world of the heroines and their interrelationships with the outside world. One of the important aspects of the analysis of women's literary work is chronotopic psychologism, a concept that combines temporal and spatial aspects (chronotope) with the image of the inner world of characters (psychologism).

The purpose of this article is to study chronotopic psychologism as a form of artistic psychologism in women's literature. Analyzing various works by female authors, we strive to reveal the specifics of using this approach to create complex and realistic images of women, explore their inner world, psychological characteristics and socio-cultural context.[1]

By studying this topic, we hope to emphasize the importance of chronotopic psychologism in the formation of empathy, empathy and understanding of female identity in literature, as well as to identify its role in expanding the literary canon and diversity of ideas about women's experience and psychology.

The concept of "chronotopic psychologism" combines two terms: "chronotope" (a concept introduced by Mikhail Bakhtin to denote a unit of artistic structure combining time and space) and "psychologism" (showing human psychology, the inner world of characters).

"Chronotopic psychologism" in women's prose can be understood as the authors' use of a peculiar combination of time, space and psychological aspects to create a special atmosphere characteristic of works of women's literature.[2]

Women's prose, like any other, can use various literary techniques, including chronotopic psychologism, to create deep and complex images and stories. The authors of women's prose can focus on the inner world of the characters, their feelings, thoughts, relationships with the outside world and other characters.

Examples of this approach can be found in the works of such writers as Virginia Woolf, Jane Austen, Sylvia Plath, Margaret Atwood and many others, whose works are distinguished by a subtle analysis of the psychology of characters and skillful use of chronotopic techniques to create a special atmosphere of works.

Virginia Woolf is an outstanding English writer whose works are often characterized by a complex structure, deep psychologism and special attention to the inner world of the characters. Her work is distinguished by the use of chronotopic psychologism, that is, a combination of elements of time, space and psychological aspects to create a unique literary atmosphere.[3]

The works of Virginia Woolf, such as "Mrs. Dalloway", "Waves", are examples of her skill in creating complex chronotopes, where time and spatial frames are intertwined with the inner world of the characters. The author's stream of consciousness technique, which she often used, allows the reader to immerse himself in the thoughts and feelings of the characters, to experience their joys, fears and doubts with them. In the novel "Mrs. Dalloway" by Virginia Woolf uses the chronotope as a way to combine the inner world of the characters with the outside world of London. The chronotope acts as a catalyst for the development of the plot and the identification of internal conflicts of the characters. Wolfe creates a complex network of time and space in which the characters' past, present and future are intertwined, as well as the hustle and bustle of the city and the inner world of their thoughts and feelings. The novel "Mrs. Dalloway" becomes not only the story of one woman's life in one day, but also an exploration of time, memory, loneliness and connections between people.

Chronotopic psychologism in the work of Virginia Woolf helps to create complex and deep images, allows you to understand the inner world of characters through the prism of their relationship with time and space. Her works are often considered classics of women's literature and an important contribution to the development of the literary trend of modernism.[4]

Chronotopic psychologism, laid down by Virginia Woolf in her works, opens up to the reader a unique opportunity to immerse himself in the inner world of the characters through the deep interaction of time and space. Wolfe not only creates picturesque images, but also builds their psychological portrait through space-time coordinates, which allows the reader to better understand the inner world of the characters and their emotional landscape.

This technique allows Wolfe to delve into the psychological aspects of his characters' lives, making them more realistic and tangible to the reader. She uses not only the characteristics of the characters, but also spatial details and the time of day or year to complement their psychological portrait and add additional nuances to the narrative.

Thanks to chronotopic psychologism, Virginia Woolf's work acquires depth and versatility, making her works not only literary masterpieces, but also unique studies of human psychology. Wolfe transforms space and time not only into decorations for his works, but also into tools for analyzing human consciousness and emotional state.[5]

Thus, chronotopic psychologism is one of the most important aspects of Virginia Woolf's work, which allows her to create works that leave a deep mark on the hearts and minds of readers, and remain relevant and inspiring even for decades after they were written.

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